

Silicon(IV) Complexes of Tridentate or Tetradentate Bifunctional Schiff Bases Derived From 2,4-Pentandione

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Monomeric penta- and hexa-coordinated $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_5(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si}(\text{SB})_2$ (where SBH_2 represents the molecule of bifunctional tridentate Schiff base) type of derivatives respectively have been synthesized by 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar reactions of silicon tetraacetate with the Schiff bases having the donor system HO-N-OH and formed by the condensation of 2,4-pentandione with *o*-aminophenol, 2-amino-4-nitrophenol, 1-hydroxy-2-butylamine and 3-hydroxy-1-propylamine. However, tetradentate Schiff bases such as bis(2, 4-pentandione) ethylenediimine and bis(2, 4-pentandione)-1, 2-propylenediimine have been found to yielded monomeric hexacoordinated $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{S}'\text{B}')$ type of complexes only (where $\text{S}'\text{B}'_2$ represents the tetradentate Schiff base molecule). The acetoxy groups of the bisacetoxy silicon Schiff base derivatives have been found to undergo replacement reactions with 2-methylpentane 2, 4-diol and the resulting complexes are hydrolytically stable. All the new derivatives have been characterized by elemental analysis, molecular weight and conductance measurements and infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectral studies.

THE literature on the Schiff base complexes of silicon is scanty. The first silicon complex of the Schiff base of aliphatic amine was reported by Breederveld¹ and later on by Kovacs *et al.*². The reactions of silicon tetrachloride with *o*-hydroxyanils were investigated by Orlova *et al.*³ and complexes of the type $\text{SiCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{L}$ (where L represents the Schiff base molecule) were isolated. However, silicon tetraacetate appears to be a more suitable starting material for the synthesis of such type of derivatives as its reactions with a number of monodentate and bidentate ligands^{4,5} have been reported to be quite facile and unlike silicon tetrahalide, it does not undergo side reactions. During the course of the present investigations, reactions of silicon tetraacetate with bifunctional tridentate (I) and bi-functional tetradentate (II) Schiff bases have been studied and several new derivatives have been synthesized for the first time. The results of these investigations are discussed in the present paper.

(where $\text{R} = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)_2$, $o\text{-C}_6\text{H}_4$ and $4\text{-NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$ and $\text{R}' = -\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2-$ and $-\text{CH}_2\text{CH}(\text{CH}_3)-$)

Experimental

Glass apparatus with standard joints was used. Adequate precautions were taken to exclude moisture from the system as both silicon tetraacetate and the Schiff base complexes are moisture sensitive. Fractionations were carried out on a ratio head by keeping the temperature of the oil bath at 110° .

Materials: Benzene (B.D.H.) was dried by refluxing over sodium wire for two days and finally distilling it azeotropically with ethanol. Silicon tetraacetate was prepared by the reaction of freshly distilled silicon tetrachloride with an excess of *t*-butylacetate⁶. It was sublimed before use and analyzed.

$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_4$: Found: Si, 10.80; OAc, 88.76
Calcd: Si, 10.63; OAc, 89.37

Preparation of Schiff bases: Schiff bases of 2,4-pentanedione with 3-hydroxy-1-propylamine and 1-hydroxy-2-butylamine were prepared by taking equimolar amounts of hydroxy alkylamine and 2,4-pentanedione in benzene and refluxing for several hours, followed by the removal of water-benzene azeotrope. Schiff bases of 2,4-pentanedione with *o*-aminophenol and 2-hydroxy-4-nitroaniline were prepared by heating equimolar amounts of the reactants in absolute alcohol for two hours and then recrystallized by the same solvent before use. Schiff bases of 2,4-pentanedione with ethylenediimine and 1,2-propylenediimine were prepared as described earlier⁷, by heating equimolar amounts of the reactants in absolute ethylether and recrystallized with

the same solvent. Their analyses and physical characteristics are reported in Table-1.

Preparation of diacetoxy silicon-Schiff base complexes: Silicon tetraacetate was dissolved in anhydrous benzene (35 ml) and the Schiff base added in equimolar ratio. After refluxing the reaction mixture for eight to ten hours, the excess of the solvent was removed on the ratio head and then under reduced pressure. The resulting products were dried at 45-50°/0.5 mm for two to three hours. The details of synthesis, analysis and the properties of the complexes are given in Table 2.

Preparation of silicon-bis-Schiff base complexes: When to a clear solution of silicon tetraacetate in anhydrous benzene (35 ml), Schiff base was added in 1 : 2 molar ratio, a normal reaction took place and a clear solution except with 4-(2-hydroxy-4-nitrophenyl) amino-3-penten-2-one was obtained. The solution was refluxed for about fourteen to sixteen hours and then the solvent removed over pump under reduced pressure. The resulting products were dried at 45-50°/0.5 mm for two to three hours. The analysis and other details are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE—1 SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR ANALYSIS

S. No.	Schiff base	Physical characteristics			Analysis [%]		
		State	M.P. [°C]	B.P. [°C/mm]	C Found [Calcd.]	H Found. [Calcd.]	N Found [Calcd.]
1.	4-(2-hydroxyphenyl) amino-3-penten-2-one (C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NO ₂)	Light yellow solid	189-191	-	68.93 (69.10)	6.81 (6.85)	7.29 (7.33)
2.	4-(2-hydroxy-4-nitro-phenyl) amino-3-penten-2-one (C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄)	Greenish yellow solid	171-172	-	55.69 (55.93)	5.08 (5.11)	11.91 (11.86)
3.	4-(1-hydroxy sec. butyl) amino-3-penten-2-one (C ₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂)	Yellow viscous liquid	-	119-20/1.5	62.99 (63.16)	9.87 (9.94)	7.98 (8.18)
4.	4-(3-hydroxypropyl) amino-3-penten-2-one (C ₈ H ₁₅ NO ₂)	Yellow viscous liquid	-	118/0.6	61.01 (61.12)	9.57 (9.61)	9.01 (8.90)
5.	bis(2, 4-pentandione)-ethylenediimine (C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂)	Colourless solid	111	-	64.20 (64.27)	8.79 (9.98)	12.75 (12.50)
6.	bis(2, 4-pentandione)-1, 2-propylenediimine (C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂)	Colourless solid	89	-	65.52 (65.49)	9.37 (9.42)	11.67 (11.78)

TABLE—2 REACTION OF SILICON TETRAACETATE WITH BIFUNCTIONAL TRIDENTATE AND BIFUNCTIONAL TETRADENTATE SCHIFF BASES IN 1 : 1 MOLAR RATIO.

S. No.	Si(OAc) ₄ [g]	Schiff base [g]	Refluxing time [hr.]	Product yield [g] and characteristics	Analysis [%]			Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
					Si Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	OAc Found (Calcd.)	
1.	2.00	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ NO ₂ 1.44	8	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₁ NO ₂) (2.40) Faint yellow solid, soluble in benzene, decomposes at 220°	8.41 (8.37)	4.05 (4.17)	34.83 (35.19)	301.7 (335.3)
2.	1.51	C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ 1.35	10	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₄) (2.03) Greenish yellow solid, sparingly soluble in benzene, decomposes at 200°	7.59 (7.38)	7.51 (7.36)	30.56 (31.54)	— (380.4)
3.	1.61	C ₉ H ₁₇ NO ₂ 1.04	8	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₉ H ₁₅ NO ₂) (1.78) Brownish yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	8.82 (8.90)	4.50 (4.44)	41.05 (39.17)	341.9 (315.4)
4.	1.46	C ₈ H ₁₅ NO ₂ 0.87	10	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₈ H ₁₃ NO ₂) (1.54) Yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	9.22 (9.31)	4.89 (4.64)	37.67 (39.15)	287.8 (301.4)
5.	1.53	C ₁₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ 1.30	8	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₂ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂) (1.98) White solid, soluble in benzene	7.90 (7.62)	7.71 (7.61)	31.58 (32.03)	392.6 (368.6)
6.	1.75	C ₁₃ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ 1.58	10	Si(OAc) ₂ (C ₁₃ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂) (2.42) Brown semi-solid, soluble in benzene	7.33 (7.34)	7.55 (7.32)	29.95 (30.84)	363.9 (382.5)

Replacement reactions of $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{S}'\text{B}')$ type of complexes with 2-methylpentane 2, 4-diol: $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{S}'\text{B}')$ type of complexes were dissolved in anhydrous benzene (40 ml) and 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol added in equimolar ratio. The mixture was then refluxed for seven to eight hours and the excess of the solvent was removed on the ratiohead and then under reduced pressure. The resulting products were dried at $50^\circ/0.05$ mm. for three hours. The details of their synthesis and analysis are recorded in Table 4.

Attempted hydrolysis of $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)$ (SB) and $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)$ (S'B') type of complexes: $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)$ (SB) and $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)$ (S'B') type of complexes were taken in a round bottomed flask and about 50 ml of water was added. No appreciable change was found to take place either in cold or on refluxing in an oil bath for several hours. The water was then removed over pump and the products dried at $60^\circ/1$ mm for two to three hours. Their elemental analysis, molecular weights, melting points and infrared spectra were found to remain unchanged.

TABLE-3 REACTION OF SILICON TETRAACETATE WITH BIFUNCTIONAL TRIDENTATE SCHIFF BASE IN 1 : 2 MOLAR RATIO

S. No.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_4$ [g]	Schiff base [g]	Refluxing time [hr.]	Product yield [g] and characteristics	Analysis [%]		Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
					Si Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	
1.	1.32	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2$ 1.92	14	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2)_2$ (1.83) Faint yellow solid, soluble in benzene melts at $248-250^\circ$	6.62 (6.90)	6.70 (6.89)	388.2 (406.6)
2.	1.43	$\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$ 2.28	15	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)$ (2.32) Yellowish grey solid, sparingly soluble in benzene, decomposes at 280°	5.83 (5.65)	11.40 (11.28)	- (496.6)
3.	1.27	$\text{C}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{NO}_2$ 1.64	14	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2)_2$ (1.75) Brownish yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	7.88 (7.66)	7.56 (7.65)	342.2 (366.6)
4.	1.15	$\text{C}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2$ 1.36	16	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2)_2$ (1.39) Yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene.	8.20 (8.29)	8.35 (8.28)	252.0 (338.6)

TABLE-4 REPLACEMENT REACTIONS OF $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{S}'\text{B}')$ TYPE OF COMPLEXES WITH 2-METHYLPENTANE-2,4-DIOL IN 1 : 1 MOLAR RATIO.

S. No.	Complex [g]	2-methyl- pentane- 2, 4-diol [g]	Refluxing time [hr.]	Product, yield [g] and characteristics	Analysis [%]		Mol. Wt. Found (Calcd.)
					Si Found (Calcd.)	N Found (Calcd.)	
1.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2)$ 1.26	0.44	7	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{11}\text{NO}_2)$ (1.08) Yellow solid, soluble in benzene, melts at 232°	8.71 (8.42)	4.33 (4.19)	346.1 (333.5)
2.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)$ 1.36	0.43	8	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4)$ (0.98) Yellow solid, sparingly soluble in benzene, decomposes at $\sim 285^\circ$	7.21 (7.41)	7.62 (7.40)	- (378.6)
3.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2)$ 1.99	0.74	8	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_9\text{H}_{15}\text{NO}_2)$ (1.70) Brownish viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	8.65 (8.95)	4.62 (4.46)	327.5 (313.6)
4.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2)$ 1.78	0.69	8	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{13}\text{NO}_2)$ (1.67) Brownish yellow viscous liquid, soluble in benzene	9.13 (9.37)	4.45 (4.67)	276.1 (299.5)
5.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)$ 1.04	0.33	8	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)$ (0.88) Brown solid, soluble in benzene, melts at $169-170^\circ$	7.64 (7.66)	8.84 (7.64)	349.7 (366.7)
6.	$\text{Si}(\text{OAc})_2(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)$ 1.45	0.45	8	$\text{Si}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2)(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2)$ (1.05) Brown semi-solid, soluble in benzene.	7.11 (7.37)	7.08 (7.36)	402.1 (380.6)

Analytical methods and physical measurements : In the resulting Schiff base complexes, silicon was estimated as silicon dioxide by direct ignition after treating the sample with few drops each of sulphuric (A. R.) and nitric acids (A. R.). For the estimation of acetoxy groups, a weighed amount of the compound was hydrolysed and then titrated against 0.05N solution of sodium hydroxide using phenolphthalein as indicator.

Nitrogen was estimated by the Kjeldahl's method and molecular weights were determined in boiling benzene by means of semi-micro ebulliometer (Gallenkamp) using thermistor sensing. The infrared spectra were scanned on a Perkin-Elmer model 337 as nujol mulls in the range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . Conductivity measurements were carried out by conductivity bridge type 235 (Anuvidyut, Roorkee) and the melting points determined in sealed tubes.

The proton magnetic resonance spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 on a Perkin-Elmer RB-12 spectrometer using TMS as the internal standard.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of silicon tetraacetate with bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases in 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 molar ratios can be represented by the following equations :

The resulting complexes are quite soluble in benzene except those obtained from 4-(2-hydroxy-4-nitrophenyl) amino-3-penten-2-one, which are only sparingly soluble. These complexes are yellow to brown in colour, and the colour deepens on keeping. The diacetoxy derivatives are readily susceptible to moisture, whereas Si(SB)_2 type of complexes appear to be quite stable. Their molecular weights as determined ebullioscopically correspond to their monomeric nature and thus in diacetoxy silicon Schiff base derivatives, the central silicon atom appears to be penta-coordinated (Fig. 1), provided the nitrogen of the $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ -group is also coordinating. However, in the silicon-bis-Schiff base derivatives, the silicon atom probably attains the usual hexacoordinated environment (Fig. 2). Further, reaction of

(Fig. 1)

(Fig. 2)

where HO-N-OH represents the Schiff base molecule

silicon tetraacetate with bifunctional tetradentate Schiff bases in 1 : 1 molar ratio can be represented as :

The above reaction in 1 : 2 molar ratio was also attempted but found to yield 1 : 1 product along with the remaining excess of the Schiff base.

Similar to the diacetoxy silicon Schiff base derivatives of bifunctional tridentate Schiff bases, these also hydrolyse readily in the atmosphere and show monomeric nature (Fig. 3) in boiling benzene.

(Fig. 3)

where HO-N-N-OH represents the Schiff base molecule

The replacement reactions of $\text{Si(OAc)}_2(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si(OAc)}_2(\text{S'B'})$ type of derivatives with 2-methylpentane-2,4-diol can be represented by following equations :

These are also monomeric in nature, quite soluble in benzene and behave as nonelectrolytes. However, as compared to the bisacetoxy Schiff base derivatives, these are quite resistant to hydrolysis and melt/decompose at higher temperatures.

Conductivity measurements : The conductance of the resulting derivatives has been determined in dimethylformamide and the results correspond to their nonelectrolytic nature.

The infrared spectra of the Schiff bases as well as the corresponding silicon complexes have been scanned and some important features may be summarized as follows :

A strong band in 1610-1595 cm^{-1} region in the Schiff bases can be attributed to the characteristic $>\text{C}=\text{N}$ -group. This remains in almost the same position or is slightly shifted towards the lower side in the silicon Schiff base derivatives.

A broad absorption band observed in the region 3550-3150 cm^{-1} in the Schiff base is attributable to the hydrogen bonded OH or NH. This, however, disappears in the complex and thereby indicating the coordination of oxygen or nitrogen to the silicon atom.

A very strong band in 1745-1700 cm^{-1} region in the case of bisacetoxy-silicon Schiff base complexes may be assigned to the $\text{C}=\text{O}$ bond of the acetoxy

group. This band is not observed in the silicon-bis-Schiff base as well as in $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_9)(\text{SB})$ and $\text{Si}(\text{C}_6\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_9)(\text{S}'\text{B}')$ type of complexes.

Some new bands of strong to medium intensity appear in the region $1140\text{-}850\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and these may be assigned to Si-O stretching⁸ vibrations.

Several new bands in the silicon-Schiff base complexes in the region $590\text{-}450\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may probably be due to δ as (Si-O-C), Si-O bending or Si-O-C torsion⁹.

PMR spectra: The mode of coordination discussed above gets further support by the PMR studies. The PMR spectra of two Schiff bases viz. 4-(2-hydroxyphenyl) amino-3-pentene-2-one and bis(2,4-pentanedione)-1, 2-propylenediimine and their

corresponding silicon complexes have been recorded in CDCl_3 and the chemical shift values (δ) are given in Table 5.

The comparison of the PMR spectrum of the Schiff base with that of its silicon complex leads to the following conclusions:

A broad peak is observed in the region $\delta 10.6\text{-}12.04$, which indicates that the Schiff base exists preferentially in the ketamine form. This is in conformity with the results reported earlier¹⁰⁻¹² also. The peak, however, disappears in the corresponding silicon complex and thus showing the coordination of nitrogen to silicon. This is further supported by the fact that the signals corresponding to the methylene and methine protons experience downfield shifting in the complexes.

TABLE—5 PMR SPECTRAL DATA OF SCHIFF BASES AND THEIR COMPLEXES IN δ (r.p.m.)

Compound	a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
(i)	2.18	5.28	1.94	7.50-6.84	7.10	12.04	-	-	-
(ii)	2.58	5.50	1.90	7.60-6.73	-	-	1.36	-	-
(iii)	2.60	5.55	1.90	7.5-6.65	-	-	-	-	-
(iv)	1.48	4.35	1.05	-	-	10.6	-	2.15	0.25 2.58
(v)	1.5-1.25	4.56	1.2	-	-	-	1.5-1.25	2.60	0.70 3.4

† Merged with CH_3 of the acetoxy groups (marked with g)

The signal at δ 7.10 in the Schiff base is assignable to the phenolic proton and this disappears in the spectra of the corresponding silicon complexes and thereby proving the deprotonation of the phenolic group and the coordination of the oxygen to the central silicon atom.

The signals observed in the region δ 1.25-1.5 in the silicon complexes are attributable to the methyl protons of the acetoxy groups.

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